

Determinants of Risk Management in Small Café Businesses in Battambang, Cambodia: Assessing Financial, Market, Operational, Reputational, and Economic Risks

Siek Darith ✉

*Department of Policy and Strategy, Ministry of Labour and Vocational Training,
Phnom Penh, Cambodia*

Lim Kim Eav ✉

*Faculty of Business Administration, Build Bright University,
Banteay Meanchey, Cambodia*

Kork Kim

Director of Build Bright University, Battambang, Cambodia

Sem Seng

Director of Build Bright University, Banteay Meanchey, Cambodia

Pou Sanith

*Department of Labour and Vocational Training Battambang Province,
Ministry of Labour and Vocational Training, Phnom Penh, Cambodia*

Abstract

Small café businesses in Battambang, Cambodia, are flourishing thanks to the city's increasing tourism and the emergence of a middle class with financial freedom. These cafes range from traditional Khmer cafés to modern Western styles. However, they encounter several management risks, especially during and after the Covid-19 pandemic. This study focuses on the major risk factors affecting small café businesses in Battambang and analyzes the effectiveness of strategies designed to mitigate these risks. Based on 80 cafés that were selected, in-depth interviews were conducted with 15 café owners, covering five key risk areas: financial, market, operational, reputational, and economic. Through surveys and in-depth interviews with café owners, the research aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the major challenges faced by these businesses and the approaches implemented to address them. The results indicate that market risk is the primary concern for café owners, followed closely by economic risk. Additionally, regression analyses of various risk factors and the quantity of café cups sold highlight several significant factors affecting small café businesses. To achieve the study's objective, the researchers conclude with strategic recommendations aimed at strengthening the risk management frameworks of café businesses in Battambang, thereby ensuring their long-term sustainability in a competitive and unpredictable market.

Keywords: *Small Café Business, Risk Management, Financial Risk, Operational Risk, Market Risk, Reputation Risk, Economic Risk, Battambang, Cambodia.*

JEL Classification codes: *G32, L26, M12, M13, D22.*

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Introduction

The rapid growth of Cambodia's coffee market is driven by multiple factors, such as the increasing number of coffee shops and cafes, higher disposable incomes, and the rising influence of Western culture (Sokly & Mardy, 2023). The economy of the country has grown significantly, with GDP doubling in a decade (1994-2004) and tripling in fifteen years (1994-2009). In 2012, the economy expanded by 7.3%, leading to a per capita GDP increase from \$760 in 2008 to \$1,300 in 2016. This growth has elevated Cambodia's status from a low-income to a lower middle-income country. By 2030 and 2050, the Royal Government of Cambodia (RGC) aims to further turn the country into a high-income and developed country. They also aim to find the right policy direction to lead the country through various political and socioeconomic challenges (MLVT, 2017; RGC, 2015). Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, Cambodia's service sector, which significantly depends on tourism and represents around 42.2% of the GDP, encountered major difficulties, including a drastic drop in tourist arrivals and a projected growth rate of just 2.88%. In response to these challenges, it is recommended that the Royal Government implement supportive measures such as providing financial aid, encouraging domestic tourism, and enhancing the quality of services. As the recovery unfolds, there are prospects for revitalization through diversification, improvements in infrastructure, and workforce development, with long-term viability hinging on skill enhancement and a stable economic framework (Ky & Lim, 2020).

Battambang, a mesmerizing city in Cambodia's northwest, is renowned for its rich cultural legacy and its flourishing coffee culture. This third-largest city in Cambodia boasts a population of 987,400 (Chhay, 2019; Darith et al., 2024; Darith & Eav, 2024). Plus, Battambang has been recognized as an exemplar in sustainable urban development in Cambodia. Its commitment to environmental sustainability and innovative planning has resulted in its designation as a clean and green city by the Cambodian government and ASEAN (Lord et al., 2024). In recent years, the café industry in Battambang City, Cambodia, has grown enormously, which is a sign of a larger expansion of the small and medium enterprises (SMEs) sector (Tieng et al., 2024). As of 2024, a café owner in Battambang claimed that the city anticipates around 150 cafés to be in operation. This growth is largely driven by a rising middle class, increasing urbanization, and a steady influx of tourists drawn to Battambang's rich cultural heritage and diverse culinary scene. These cafés not only serve as popular social gathering places but also play a crucial role in creating employment opportunities, particularly for young people and women, significantly contributing to the local labor market. Based on the global scale, small café businesses worldwide have a significant economic impact. They contribute to farmers in the community, provide jobs, and attract tourists, all of which result in benefits to local economies. Furthermore, the coffee sector supports millions of jobs globally (Sachs et al., 2019; Darith et al., 2024).

Despite the positive context for the growth of the café industry in Cambodia, particularly in Battambang, small cafés face a range of risks, including economic volatility, strong competition, supply chain issues, and obstacles to regulation (Parizat, 2015; Sokly & Mardy, 2023; Statista, 2024). Comparably, as per Nestlé ESAR (2024) report, the global coffee market is under increasing pressure to adopt sustainable strategies and raise prices. In the same way, financial challenges pose significant threats to its long-term stability for small café owners in Battambang face difficulties securing adequate funding, hindering their ability to sustain or expand their businesses (Union, 2010; Parizat, 2015). A recent survey revealed that 60.2% of respondents in the type of restaurant

business sector struggle with financial instability, which is evidence of more significant debt levels due to insufficient cash flow and limited access to capital. This is consistent with the World Bank's findings regarding Cambodia's private sector debt levels, highlighting the necessity for enhanced bank supervision and stress testing to maintain financial stability. The increasing debt among restaurant owners illustrates the financial challenges they encounter in an unpredictable economic climate (CIR, 2024; CCT, 2020). Cafés often face challenges in implementing effective marketing strategies to attract and retain customers, which can worsen their financial risks. Beyond financial risks, the café industry also faces market risks, including changes in consumer tastes, increased competition, and variations in demand due to seasonal trends (Peluso, 2023; Poltronieri & Rossi, 2016). In this competitive environment, café owners must constantly innovate and adjust to evolving consumer preferences, a challenge that can be particularly overwhelming for small business operators (Bianco, 2020; Ramgade & DY, 2021). Besides, operational risks play a key role in determining the profitability and stability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), including café businesses. Managing supply chains effectively is vital, as disruptions can cause delays, increase costs, and erode customer trust. To mitigate these risks, businesses can diversify their suppliers and maintain inventory buffers (Hudáková et al., 2023; Adam & Alarifi, 2021; Falkner & Hiebl, 2015).

Reputational risk in the café industry is influenced by some critical factors. Incidents related to food safety, such as contamination or improper handling of allergens, can significantly tarnish a café's reputation, highlighting the importance of rigorous food safety measures (Gatzert, 2015). Additionally, poor customer service, characterized by rude or inattentive staff and long wait times, can result in negative word-of-mouth and online reviews, greatly affecting the café's reputation (Cullerton, 2024). Negative social media reviews and crises can also escalate quickly, causing considerable reputational harm, which underscores the need for proactive engagement and effective crisis management (Gaultier-Gaillard et al., 2009). Also, ethical and social issues, such as labor exploitation, environmental harm, or a lack of social responsibility, can adversely impact public perception, emphasizing the necessity for ethical business practices and corporate social responsibility efforts (Trcak, 2020). In these circumstances, engaging in CSR activities can effectively manage reputational risk. SMEs that are actively involved in CSR initiatives can cultivate a positive reputation and set themselves apart from their competitors (Sarbutts, 2003).

This study aims to address a significant knowledge gap in understanding the primary risk management practices employed by small café businesses in Battambang. By identifying and assessing the most critical financial, operational, reputational, market, and economic risks faced by these businesses, this research provides café owners with actionable insights to enhance their resilience. The findings will empower café owners to adopt proactive risk management strategies, thereby increasing their chances of long-term success in a competitive market. Ultimately, the findings of this study are expected to contribute to the economic resilience and growth of Battambang's service sector, fostering an environment where café businesses can thrive and prosper, even in the face of adversity.

Literature Review

Risk management refers to locating, evaluating, and reducing risks that might affect the objectives of the company. This involves evaluating risks related to finances, operations, and strategy and setting plans in place to reduce their impact (Rais, 2014; Verbano & Venturini, 2013; Kaplan & Mikes, 2016).

Financial management involves organizing, planning, supervising, and controlling financial operations. This covers budget planning, financial data analysis, investment decision-making, and risk management. The objective is to assist companies in meeting their financial goals and keeping

a healthy cash flow (Grozdanovska et al., 2017). Financial risks stem from managing assets and liabilities, arising from market shifts, credit defaults, and liquidity shortages. These risks can significantly impact an organization's stability and profitability, necessitating robust risk management strategies. Businesses often implement hedging techniques and diversify their portfolios to mitigate potential losses and ensure financial resilience (Rampini et al., 2021).

Market management is part of understanding and influencing market trends. To address customer wants and gain a competitive edge, this involves developing marketing strategies, segmenting the market, and positioning products (Zhang & Chang, 2020). Additionally, market research plays a crucial role in identifying consumer preferences and behaviors, allowing companies to tailor their offerings effectively. By continuously monitoring market dynamics, businesses can adapt their strategies to meet changing demands and remain ahead of competitors (Ramos et al., 2023). Market risks involve fluctuations in stock prices, interest rates, and exchange rates, which can impact a business's financial health. For instance, a café reliant on seasonal trends could suffer reduced revenue during market downturns. Credit risk arises from the possibility of loan or credit defaults, affecting the business's cash flow and stability (Hubbard, 2009).

Operational management is charged with overseeing day-to-day operations and procedures to make certain a business runs effectively. In order to achieve operational objectives while keeping high quality, this includes overseeing production, inventory, quality control, and resource optimization (Garvin, 1998). According to Batato et al., (2023), it is crucial to adapt operational strategies to meet changing demands while maintaining high quality. This adaptability not only enhances customer satisfaction but also fosters resilience within the organization. As markets evolve, embracing innovative approaches can lead to sustainable growth and a competitive edge. Operational risk essentially refers to the possibility of experiencing a loss due to external factors or inadequate or unsuccessful operations, personnel, or procedures. This covers risks like fraud, legal issues, cyberattacks, and natural disasters (Abdymomunov & Mihov, 2017).

Reputational management is the image of a business that may be impacted by its internal practices. If left unchecked, poor customer service or poor products could lead to negative feedback and potentially damage the café's reputation. Keeping a positive reputation requires efficient administration of internal protocols (Eccles et al., 2007; Men, 2014). Reputational risks can damage a business's public image and how customers perceive it. These risks can stem from bad customer service, product quality problems, or unethical behavior. For instance, a café with consistently poor reviews due to subpar service or quality may suffer a tarnished reputation, leading to decreased customer loyalty and sales. Moreover, ethical concerns or scandals, such as accusations of unsanitary conditions, can seriously harm a business's reputation and brand value (Men, 2014; Hubbard, 2009).

Economic management involves the strategic planning and implementation of policies to control and stabilize an economy while addressing various economic risks that can lead to financial loss or instability. These risks include market fluctuations, political instability, and natural disasters (Liou, 1998). Effective economic management requires a thorough assessment of macroeconomic risks, understanding the critical drivers of potential risks, and developing strategies to navigate them. Integrating disaster risk management into economic policies is also crucial for protecting economic growth and development, which involves risk assessment, prevention, mitigation strategies, and preparedness (Bryson & Edwards, 2017). Furthermore, risk management significantly impacts economic decision-making, as it is a critical element influencing project-based environments and overall economic stability (Galli & Battiloro, 2019).

Methods

Sampling and Data Collection

This study focuses on small café businesses in Battambang. A sample of 80 cafés was selected using purposive and convenience sampling techniques within a non-random sampling framework. In-depth interviews were conducted with 15 café owners to explore five key risk areas in their risk management practices. The sample size is large enough to gather diverse information on management practices while remaining small enough to enable a detailed examination of each business's risk management strategies. The sample was selected using a non-random sampling method that combined purposive and convenience sampling. Cafés were chosen based on specific criteria including size, location, and financial, market, operational, reputational, and economic experiences, while convenience sampling ensured participation from cafés that were accessible and willing to be interviewed. Furthermore, we employed a closed-ended questionnaire to gather quantitative data, which measured various aspects of their risk management practices. This structured approach allowed for standardized data collection and facilitated comparison across businesses. Also, we conducted open-ended questionnaires with semi-structured interviews involving the owners or managers of the cafés. These interview methods provided in-depth insights into how café owners perceive and manage risks. While interview questions were prepared in advance, they were flexible to adapt to each owner's unique experiences, allowing for detailed, qualitative insights into the practical aspects of their risk management strategies.

Model and Data Analysis

All data from the study were using STATA software version 17 for data generation and regression and analysis. Based on Wooldridge (2009), Hucheson (2011), Stock (2015), and Siek (2024), widely used tools in econometrics, multiple regression models using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) are considered to relate individual performance to coffee income as dependent variables and a series of independent variables associated with financial, market, operational, reputational, and economic risks in coffee small businesses. The constructed models present the econometric analysis in the following way:

$$Income = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Q1 + \beta_2 \cdot Q2 + \beta_3 \cdot Q3 + \beta_4 \cdot Q4 + \beta_5 \cdot Q5 + \beta_6 \cdot Q6 + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where:

β_0 is the intercept.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_6$ are the coefficients for each independent variable.

ϵ_i represents the error term.

The econometric model uses the constants $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_6$ to represent the coefficients of parameters that show how income in small cafés in Battambang is related to different risk management practices. The variable ϵ_i represents an error term that is assumed to follow a logistic distribution. The model can be written as an equation like (1), where Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5, and Q6 are variables that represent different risk management practices.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 provides descriptive statistics for café owners' perceptions of various factors affecting risk management practices among café businesses in Battambang. The data is based on a 5-point Likert scale (1=very low-5=very high) for questions Q1-Q6. Initially, Q1 represents confidence in risk management, yielding a mean score of 3.47 with a standard deviation of 1.06. The financial stability rating (Q2) yielded a mean score of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 0.86, indicating a moderate level of confidence in financial stability among the cafés. In terms of supply chain issue frequency (Q3), the mean score of 3.13 suggests that owners rate supply chain concerns as quite frequent, with a standard deviation of 0.64. Interestingly, marketing strategy effectiveness (Q4) received a neutral mean score of 3.07 with minimal variability and a standard deviation of 0.26. The local economy (Q5) exhibits sensitivity, with a mean score of 3.27, indicating awareness of the economic impacts on the café business. Following that, café reputation (Q6) shows the highest mean score of 3.67 with a standard deviation of 0.62, indicating that café owners generally consider their reputations advantageous.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Input for the Independent Variable Regression

Variable	Definition	%					Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.
		1	2	3	4	5			
Q1	Confidence in risk management	0	20	33	27	20	15	3.47	1.06
Q2	Financial stability rating	1	20	45	27	7	15	3.20	0.86
Q3	Supply chain issue frequency	0	13	60	27	0	15	3.13	0.64
Q4	Marketing strategy effectiveness	0	0	93	7	0	15	3.07	0.26
Q5	Sensitivity to the local economy	1	7	65	20	7	15	3.27	0.70
Q6	Café reputation	0	7	20	73	0	15	3.67	0.62

Note: 1: Very low, 2: Low, 3: Neutral, 4: High, 5: Very High

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics related to the sales performance of café businesses in Battambang. The data consists of key indicators, including daily sales volume, total daily revenues, and daily income. The variable *Amount_cups*, representing the total number of cups sold per day (sales quantity per day), has a mean of 88.00 cups with a standard deviation of 81.08. This demonstrates significant variation in daily sales performance among the cafés, with a minimum of 10 cups and a maximum of 300 cups, reflecting disparities in customer demand. The "Revenues" variable, representing total daily revenue in dollars (total revenue per day), has a mean of \$90.17 and a standard deviation of \$69.11. Daily revenue ranges from \$10 to \$200, indicating significant variation across cafés. In this scenario, some cafés make significant cash, while others strive to achieve significant sales. The "Income" variable, representing total daily income in dollars (total income per day), has a mean of 40.50 and a standard deviation of 29.59, with the income value ranging from \$3.80 to \$88. Overall, these numbers demonstrate the significant financial differences within the café businesses. Individuals also show how small cafés run their businesses and what factors affect their sales performance in the local market.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Output for the Dependent Variable Regression

Variable	Definition	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Amount_cups</i>	Sales quantity per day (cups)	15	88.00	81.08	10	300
Revenues	Total revenue per day (\$)	15	90.17	69.11	10	200
Income	Total income per day (\$)	15	40.50	29.59	3.8	88

The Biggest Risks Faced and Sales Operations in Small Café Businesses in Battambang

Understanding the biggest risks faced by small café businesses is crucial for their success. Figure 1 below displays the percentage of the biggest risks faced by café businesses. These risks include financial, market, operational, reputational, and economic. By being aware of these risks, café owners can come up with ways to reduce them, which will help their businesses stay open and make money in the long run. Remarkably, market risk is the most prominent, reaching 40% of responses. Café owners are likely concerned about competition, consumer preferences, and economic changes. Subsequently, economic risk reached 27%, indicating that external economic factors also weigh heavily on these businesses. Reputational and financial risks each reached 13% of the responses, reflecting concerns about protecting a positive image and financial stability. Operational risk is the least significant, at 7%, which means that café owners may not face as many severe operational challenges.

Figure 1. Biggest Risks Faced in Small Café Businesses in Battambang.

Source: Authors, 2024

The sales operations of small café businesses in Battambang also play a crucial role in the study. Figure 2 displays information about the length of time each café store has been actively operating. The duration of operation for each café ranges from 0.3 to 12 years. Surprisingly, compared to the others, Thy Thy coconut Café has been operating for 12 years. Following that, Teatime Café has been operating for 10 years. This reveals an active presence in the local market. However, several cafés that have been operating for less than 3 years, among them Maddee Café, Kooji Café station, Café 143, and Sompov Café Brand, are fairly new. The chart points out the level of experience that various Battambang cafés operate, emphasizing both seasoned and new cafés in the market.

Figure 2. Sales Operations in Small Café Businesses in Battambang.
Source: Authors, 2024

The Risk Factors Affecting Small Café Businesses

Owners of small café businesses in Battambang Province, Cambodia, may lower risks, make wiser choices, and improve success by being aware of the risk factors. Table 3 presents the results of a regression analysis of various risk factors affecting small café businesses' income. Six key independent variables are still included in the table. Q1-Q6. Significantly, confidence in risk management (Q1) found the highest level of positive significance at 1%, exhibiting a coefficient of 0.591 and a p-value of 0.005. According to Tokar Asaad, (2015), financial literacy, including financial confidence, is heavily influenced by financial decisions. Individuals who exaggerate their financial knowledge often engage in riskier financial behaviors, potentially affecting their income. The higher confidence in financial decisions is linked to higher risk tolerance. This may result in more potential profits but also a larger chance of losses, which could affect total income (Sharma et al., 2024). The findings indicate that a higher confidence in risk management is associated with an effect on income and overall financial performance. Similarly, the financial stability rating (Q2) also found positive significance at 5%, with a coefficient of 0.406 and a p-value of 0.069. Despite being significantly lower than Q1, this variable confirms café businesses with greater financial stability tend to achieve better performance. Financial stability has a significant influence on business performance and is determined by business knowledge and orientation. Strong financial management and entrepreneurial skills typically result in higher financial performance for cafés (Poernomo et al., 2019). Supply chain issue frequency (Q3) has a substantial positive coefficient of 0.868 and a p-value of 0.012, with the significance level at 5%. In this case, supply chain issue may result in higher costs for supplies, raw materials, and transportation, which may be affecting income. According to Katsaliaki et al. (2021), and Nguyen & Sarker (2018), supply chain issue, which are becoming more frequent and severe, are causing significant challenges for various industries, including cafés. These issues, triggered by factors such as natural disasters, political conflicts, and global health crises, can result in substantial financial losses for cafés. Delayed

deliveries, spoilage of perishable goods, and the need to seek alternative suppliers can lead to increased costs, reduced profit margins, and ultimately, lower overall income. To safeguard their operations, cafés can implement resilience strategies like diversifying their supplier base, maintaining sufficient inventory levels, and leveraging technology to enhance supply chain visibility and management. The final variable, café reputation (Q6) has a coefficient of 0.568 with a p-value of 0.076, highlighting its level of significance at 5%. Basically, Café's reputation significantly affects its income, as it also directly influences customer views and practices. Positive customer experiences strongly affect perceptions of value, satisfaction, and loyalty toward a café. When customers have positive interactions, it enhances the café's reputation, leading to increased customer satisfaction and repeat visits, ultimately boosting the café's income (Zhang, 2017). Similarly, another study by Mayasari et al. (2022) on Indonesian coffee shops revealed that factors like service quality, ambiance, and preference for local brands significantly impact customer satisfaction and loyalty. Cafés can enhance customer satisfaction and income by cultivating a robust reputation based on these factors.

Table 3. The Regression Analysis of Risk Factors Affecting Small Café Businesses' Income.

Variable	Definition	Coefficient	Std. Err.	T-value	P-value	
Q1	Confidence in risk management	β_1 0.591***	0.152	3.880	0.005	
Q2	Financial stability rating	β_2 0.406**	0.194	2.100	0.069	
Q3	Supply chain issue frequency	β_3 0.868**	0.267	3.260	0.012	
Q4	Marketing strategy effectiveness	β_4 -1.100	0.710	-1.550	0.160	
Q5	Sensitivity to the local economy	β_5 -0.399	0.260	-1.530	0.164	
Q6	Café reputation	β_6 0.568**	0.279	2.030	0.076	
_cons	Constants	β_0 -0.101	3.147	-0.030	0.975	
Prob > F		0.0188				
R-squared		0.7943				
Adj R-squared		0.6401				
Root MSE		0.55965				

Note: *10% level significant; **5% level significant; ***1% level significant

Table 4 presents the results of a regression analysis on how the quantity of café cups sold affects the operations of small café businesses. The regression analysis in Table 3 further enhances the clear understanding of the significant relationship between sold cafés and business performance. Particularly, both confidence in risk management (Q1) and supply chain issue frequency (Q3) exhibited the highest level of statistical significance at the 1% level, suggesting a significant positive correlation with the result of the variable. Cafés that implement strong risk management practices often see an increase in sales. This result corroborates existing literature that emphasizes that cafés that implement strong risk management practices often see an increase in sales. Effective inventory management and supply chain strategies enhance customer satisfaction and encourage repeat business, leading to higher sales volumes. This relationship is frequently statistically significant, indicating that as confidence in risk management grows, so does the number of cups sold (Parizat et al., 2015). This relationship shows that improved risk management not only improves operational efficiency but also has a positive influence on consumer behavior. As a result, businesses may profit from investing in effective risk management alternatives to increase sales and performance. Likewise, the financial stability rating (Q2), which is based on the quantity of café cups, stated a positive significance level of 10%. Cafés with financial stability can invest in higher-quality cups that are more resilient, eye-catching, and more sustainable. This can boost customer satisfaction and brand loyalty, encouraging higher cup sales (Ghoshray & Mohan, 2021; Sangalang & Fampo, 2024; Poernomo et al., 2019). In essence, financial stability promotes successful

marketing campaigns that advertise the café and its products and services (Swaminathan et al., 2022; Sangalang & Fampo, 2024). Cafés that have proved financially independent may expand their business by opening more branches (Yellen, 2023; Darith et al., 2024).

Table 4. The Regression Analysis of Quantity of Café Cups Sold.

Variable	Definition	Coefficient		Std. Err.	T-value	P-value
Q1	Confidence in risk management	β_1	0.652***	0.116	5.640	0.000
Q2	Financial stability rating	β_2	0.252*	0.147	1.710	0.126
Q3	Supply chain issue frequency	β_3	0.911***	0.203	4.490	0.002
Q4	Marketing strategy effectiveness	β_4	-0.593	0.540	-1.100	0.304
Q5	Sensitivity to the local economy	β_5	-0.152	0.198	-0.770	0.464
Q6	Café reputation	β_6	0.184	0.212	0.870	0.411
_cons	Constants	β_0	-0.129	2.392	-0.050	0.958
Prob > F		0.005				
R-squared		0.858				
Adj R-squared		0.751				
Root MSE		0.425				

Note: *10% level significant; **5% level significant; ***1% level significant

Conclusions

This study addresses the multifaceted factors of risk management in small café businesses in Battambang, Cambodia. Based on 80 cafés that were selected, in-depth interviews were conducted with 15 café owners, covering five key risk areas: financial, market, operational, reputational, and economic. It extends valuable insights for mitigating potential risks and ensuring the long-term sustainability of small cafés in Battambang. Additionally, the sales operations of small café businesses in Battambang also play a crucial role in the study. Unpredictably, the length of operation for each coffee shop. Each café operates for a duration ranging from 0.3 to 12 years. The regression analysis conducted in this study uncovers significant various risk factors that affect café businesses' income and the quantity of café cups sold. It revealed that confidence in risk management and financial stability are key determinants, closely followed by supply chain issue frequency and café reputation. By proactively addressing risks, café businesses in Battambang can improve their overall management, financial performance, secure funding, and allocate resources effectively. To strengthen the resilience of small café businesses, it is necessary for owners to critically master risk management strategies that can assist in handling the challenges posed by a changing and unpredictable business environment.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the significant risk factors affecting small cafés in Battambang as well as laying a foundation for future research. By identifying these risks and recommending effective mitigation strategies, the study contributes to the sustainable growth and development of the local café industry.

Recommendations

According to the study's results, small café businesses in Battambang can greatly enhance their resilience and ensure long-term sustainability by adopting these recommendations:

Emphasize risk management; café owners should treat risk management as a fundamental aspect of their business operations. By crafting detailed risk management strategies, they can proactively identify, evaluate, and address potential threats. This involves performing regular risk evaluations,

creating contingency plans, and enforcing strong financial controls. Providing risk management training and education for employees can further improve their capacity to handle unexpected challenges.

Cultivate strong supplier relationships; keeping strong connections with suppliers is essential for maintaining a steady and high-quality supply of ingredients. By diversifying their supplier base and negotiating advantageous terms, café owners can minimize supply chain interruptions and lower costs. Effective communication and collaboration with suppliers can also help in recognizing potential risks and devising strategies to lessen their impact on the business.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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